

A Case for Assessing General Cognitive Ability in Audiology

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Background noise is a near-constant obstacle interfering with successful speech understanding, whether it be from the roar of traffic, the din of construction, or the chatter of fellow patrons in a busy restaurant. The ability to understand speech in noise (SIN) is not a purely sensory one; rather, it also requires the support of cognitive resources. Despite this, audiologists rarely assess cognition in their patients. While researchers are increasingly considering the cognitive contributions to speech perception, their focus continues to be on specific cognitive abilities, in particular working memory (WM) capacity. In this paper, I will argue that, instead, general cognitive ability (likely underpin by a range of domain-general cognitive resources) may be the crucial faculty supporting SIN performance. As a result, assessing general cognitive ability should be common practice among audiologists. I will discuss the background and rationale for such an assessment, how it should be designed, and how it could be implemented by audiologists to inform diagnosis and treatment.

Introduction to Speech-in-Noise Perception

To begin, I will discuss what underpins listeners' ability to understand SIN, including the sensory and other factors that are known to predict this ability. This will lead us into a discussion of general intelligence and the cognitive predictors of SIN perception.

Audiometric Hearing Loss

To detect hearing loss, the primary diagnostic tool of clinical audiologists is pure-tone audiometry—a test in which patients respond when presented with quiet pure tones (Parmar et al., 2022). This is carried out in each ear and across a range of frequencies to define a patient's audiogram, describing their hearing ability (Gelfand & Calandruccio, 2022). This test effectively captures patients' hearing threshold across these conditions; that is, the level below which a patient cannot reliably detect pure tones. This is in contrast to suprathreshold testing, which assesses patients' ability to accurately perceive sounds at a level they can readily hear. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), a patient has hearing loss if their absolute threshold is elevated by 20 dB or more (averaged across a range of frequencies, generally 0.5, 1, 2, and 4 kHz) in either ear (WHO, 2023). By this criterion, approximately 30% of the global population over the age of 60 has diagnosable hearing loss (WHO, 2023).

This definition of hearing loss, by focusing on elevated thresholds, ignores other aspects of hearing ability. Indeed, the most common complaint by patients visiting audiologists is not reduced sensitivity to pure tones, but rather trouble understanding speech in the presence of background noise (Houtgast & Festen, 2008). Despite audiometry being the primary tool of audiologists, SIN perception is regularly found to be weakly or non-significantly correlated with audiometric hearing loss (Blandy & Lutman, 2005; Dubno et al., 1984; Vermiglio et al., 2012). As a result, two listeners with similar hearing thresholds can differ greatly in their SIN performance. Not surprisingly, then, more than 10% of patients reporting impaired SIN performance do not have audiometric hearing loss (Tremblay et al., 2015). These cases may be referred to as “subclinical” hearing loss (Plack, 2018). With SIN testing routinely used by less than 15% of American audiologists (Beck, 2017; Clark et al., 2017), subclinical patients are

often turned away without treatment (Parthasarathy et al., 2020). Thus, it is likely that far more people have hearing loss than audiologists are currently able to detect.

Hidden Hearing Loss

Why is SIN performance not well predicted by audiometric hearing loss? Only some pathologies that lead to impaired SIN performance also elevate pure-tone thresholds. For instance, age-related damage to the cochlea's inner or outer hair cells reduces patients' sensitivity to pure tones, which can be readily diagnosed via elevated thresholds that worsen in higher frequencies (Plack, 2018). In contrast, cochlear synaptopathy is a condition, first discovered in mice, in which noise exposure does not damage the inner hair cells themselves, but rather the synapses between inner hair cells and auditory nerve fibres going to the brain (Kujawa & Liberman, 2009). Research in guinea pigs has found that this damage primarily affects low-spontaneous rate and high-threshold fibres, sparing high-spontaneous rate and low-threshold fibres (Furman et al., 2013). Those damaged fibres are important to encoding acoustic information at higher levels and in background noise (Young & Barta, 1986), while the preserved fibres are important to detecting low-level sounds such as those used in audiometry (Sachs & Abbas, 1974). As a result, cochlear synaptopathy may lead to SIN problems despite normal audiograms (Plack et al., 2014). That said, the evidence of a link between cochlear synaptopathy and SIN impairment in humans is limited (Guest et al., 2018).

Cochlear synaptopathy, with its selective effects on suprathreshold perception, is often referred to as "hidden hearing loss" (Schaette & McAlpine, 2011). However, when defined more broadly, hidden hearing loss can refer to any deficits causing hearing impairments that are not detectable via pure-tone audiometry, not only cochlear synaptopathy (Kohrman et al., 2020). When defined in this broader way, hidden hearing loss is similar to the "distortion" component in Plomp's (1978) two-component model of speech intelligibility. Plomp observed that listeners' SIN performance was often poorer than expected based on the audibility of the speech, which can be affected by factors such as hearing loss or background noise. His two-factor model described these audibility-related factors as "attenuation" (threshold deficits), while describing any remaining, unexplained deficits as "distortion" (suprathreshold deficits).

If pure-tone audiometry cannot explain SIN performance, what can? Alternative causes of hidden hearing loss have mostly focused on other pathologies along the ascending auditory pathway, such as auditory nerve demyelination, elevated central gain, and auditory neural maladaptation (Valderrama et al., 2022). As a result, other attempts to account for variance in SIN performance have focused on tests of auditory perception, in particular suprathreshold tests. For instance, pairing patients' audiograms with their performance on auditory figure-ground tests explains approximately 50% of the variance in SIN performance in both younger and older adults, suggesting that acoustic grouping abilities play a role (Holmes & Griffiths, 2019). Similarly, pairing pure-tone audiometry with the Audible Contrast Threshold Test also explains about 50% of the variance in SIN performance (Zaar, personal communication). This test measures the ability to detect spectro-temporal modulations imposed on a noise carrier sound, mirroring many of the skills required for SIN perception (Zaar et al., 2023).

Cognitive Hearing Science

Hidden hearing loss, as well as distortion, can be conceptualized even more broadly to encompass non-auditory factors relevant to SIN performance, such as cognition (Griffiths, 2023;

Houtgast & Festen, 2008). Speech understanding is not only about whether the speech is audible. Presented with variable and continuous streams of speech input, listeners must be able to separate target speech from competing sounds; segment it into phonemes, syllables, and words; disambiguate any unclear utterances; and process it as a coherent whole (Johnsrude & Rodd, 2016; Van Hedger & Johnsrude, 2022). Indeed, the interaction between cognition and auditory perception has long been acknowledged. Over a century ago, Spearman (1904) demonstrated that private school students' general academic ability (an average of all course grades) strongly positively correlated with pitch discrimination ability (judged by music teachers; $r = .94$). In the decades that followed, speech perception was shown to be supported by an array of cognitive processes, including attention (Broadbent, 1958; Cherry, 1953; Treisman, 1960) as well as memory (Rabbitt, 1968; Salamé & Baddeley, 1987; Warren, 1970).

Interest in the cognition-hearing interaction heightened after 1988, when the Working Group on Speech Understanding and Aging wrote an influential report (Committee on Hearing, Bioacoustics, and Biomechanics, 1988) highlighting the role of cognition in speech perception (Akeroyd, 2008). This led to the eventual emergence of cognitive hearing science, an interdisciplinary field integrating cognition into models of speech perception and hearing (Arlinger et al., 2009). Research investigating the cognitive contributions to speech perception exploded over this period, with the number of articles in major hearing journals more than quadrupling from 2001–2005 to 2011–2015 (Füllgrabe & Rosen, 2016b). This is consistent with a more widespread shift to a cognitive approach to the study of perception, including visual perception, and especially as it relates to aging (Roberts & Allen, 2016). A great many cognitive models of speech perception have since been put forward (Heald & Nusbaum, 2014; Pichora-Fuller et al., 2016; Rönnberg et al., 2013; Wingfield & Tun, 2007).

The most influential cognitive model of speech perception is the Ease of Language Understanding Model (Rönnberg et al., 1998, 2013, 2022). This model proposes that multimodal speech is first bound into a unified representation. If there is a clear match between that input and phonological and lexical long-term representations, speech understanding is easy and effortless. However, if a match does not easily occur (e.g., due to hearing loss or background noise), WM is crucial to disambiguation, along with other executive processes. WM is multifaceted, including both the domain-specific storage of information and the domain-general processing of information (Baddeley, 2000; Baddeley & Hitch, 1974). According to the Ease of Language Understanding Model, one of the roles of WM is postdictive, allowing for degraded speech input to be held in an active state while other forms of processing allow inferences to be made about the meaning of any unclear utterances (Stenfelt & Rönnberg, 2009).

The inclusion of cognition has succeeded in explaining more variance in SIN performance. One early study was Smoorenburg (1992), which studied younger and middle-aged adults with noise-induced hearing loss. They found that high-frequency loss was a moderate-to-strong predictor of speech reception threshold (SRT) in noise ($r = .72$). When also including a factor derived from the covariance in SRT across both ears (as well as measurement error, which was estimated using principal component analysis and equipment field testing), 100% of the variance in SIN performance was explained. The author attributed that common factor to “central factors” (pg. 434), including but perhaps not limited to cognitive abilities related to speech perception. However, no recent studies (most of which have tested older adults) have been able to explain SIN performance to that extent. A combination of auditory and cognitive factors are usually thought to explain, at best, 70% of the variance in SIN performance (Houtgast & Festen,

2008; Humes, 2002). Even when measurement error is considered, it is not likely that much more variance would be explained (e.g., Festen & Plomp, 1983). Consistent with these numbers, others have speculated that, in hearing-impaired listeners, approximately two-thirds of the explained variance in SIN performance may be attributable to high-frequency hearing loss, with the remaining third cognition (Akeroyd, 2008; Van Rooij & Plomp, 1990).

Introduction to General Intelligence

In the previous section, I discussed how SIN performance is not adequately explained by pure-tone audiometry. Beyond audiometric hearing loss, including suprathreshold factors explains approximately 50% of SIN performance, with cognitive factors bringing this to 70%. Given the demonstrated ability of cognitive factors to predict SIN performance, it will be fruitful to discuss the structure of intelligence before moving further. This will offer us a framework on which to understand how cognition may support SIN performance.

Overview of the g-factor

More than a century of research shows that when participants are given a battery of diverse cognitive tests, their scores covary positively; this is known as the positive manifold (Jensen, 1998). First observed by Charles Spearman (Spearman, 1904), it has since become perhaps the most frequently and consistently replicated finding in all of psychology (Schneider & McGrew, 2018). Spearman (1904) observed that students who perform well in one school subject tend to perform well in others. He invented the statistical method of factor analysis to describe this pattern, finding that a general intelligence factor, or g-factor, explained 40–50% of the variance in academic performance. More recent research has found a similar percentage of performance explained (Deary et al., 2010; Jensen, 1998). In addition, Spearman proposed several domain-specific factors that are relevant to specific tasks, explaining task-specific performance left unaccounted for by the g-factor (Spearman, 1904).

While Spearman called this factor general intelligence, it is synonymously referred to as general cognitive ability, a term I will also use. Statistically, the positive manifold underlying general intelligence is described by the g-factor. In turn, the g-factor is approximated by intelligence quotient (IQ) tests, the most common being the Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale–Fourth Edition (WAIS-IV; Wechsler, 2008). The WAIS-IV includes 10 core subtests, which can be grouped into four index scores (Verbal Comprehension, WM, Perceptual Reasoning, and Processing Speed) as well as a full-scale IQ score. The more diverse the tests employed, the better the IQ estimate (Major et al., 2011). This is because it minimizes the influence of task-specific abilities, revealing a general intelligence factor. A raw score can be calculated for all 10 core subtests, which are generally compared to age norms to arrive at a normed score. These normed scores are then added together to calculate an age-normed IQ.

Despite a history of controversy (see Murdoch, 2007), IQ is one of the human traits that is most predictive of life outcomes. For instance, higher IQ is associated with higher academic success, educational attainment, job performance, and income (Berry & Sackett, 2009; Brown et al., 2021; Irwing & Lynn, 2006; Lubinski, 2009; Ones et al., 2005; Schmidt & Hunter, 1998). In addition, IQ is strongly linked to various health outcomes, with a one standard deviation increase in childhood IQ associated with a 24% decrease in their risk of death from all causes (Calvin et al., 2011). This includes not only a reduced rate of death from illnesses such as heart disease and stroke, but also rate of death from injury and suicide (Calvin et al., 2017).

The Structure of Intelligence

Spearman's work led into another highly influential theory of intelligence: Cattell and Horn's theory of fluid and crystallized intelligences (Gf-Gc theory). Raymond Cattell, a student of Spearman, began by arguing that general intelligence should be subdivided into two broad cognitive abilities: fluid intelligence (Gf), using general reasoning to solve an unfamiliar problem; and crystallized intelligence (Gc), applying prior knowledge to solve a problem (Cattell, 1941, 1943). This theory was meant not to contradict Spearman's g-factor, but rather to elaborate on it. Indeed, even Spearman (1904) acknowledged that different forms of intelligence may constitute the g-factor. Cattell did no further research on this topic for 20 years (Cattell, 1963), at which point he began a fruitful collaboration with his student, John Horn. Horn (1965, 1968), on top of Gf and Gc, added five more abilities to Gf-Gc theory: speed of processing, short-term memory, long-term storage and retrieval, visual processing, and auditory processing. Other broad abilities were later included, such as reaction time/decision speed, quantitative reasoning (Horn, 1991), as well as reading/writing (Woodcock, 1994).

As Gf-Gc theory became fully developed, another theory emerged: Carroll's three-strata theory of intelligence (Carroll, 1993, 1997). This theory emphasized the hierarchical nature of intelligence, dividing it into three strata, or levels. Within each lower-level stratum, cognitive abilities correlate with one another in such a way that allows them to define and estimate higher-level strata (Gustafsson & Undheim, 1996). Stratum I consists of narrow abilities; that is, highly specific and specialized skills. These narrow abilities are themselves measured using different cognitive tests, which are not part of the hierarchy. Stratum II consists of broad cognitive abilities, such as those discussed in Gf-Gc theory. Finally, stratum III is the g-factor. While Gf-Gc theory consists of a single level and does not include a g-factor in its model, three-strata theory does. In three-strata theory, broad cognitive abilities are generally overlapping those described in Gf-Gc theory, but with some differences. Notably, three-strata theory considers quantitative knowledge to be a component of Gf and considers reading/writing to be a form of Gc, leading to a smaller number of broad abilities than Gf-Gc theory.

Despite their differences, the Gf-Gc and three-strata theories have many similarities and are generally compatible. For this reason, McGrew et al. (1997) first tried to combine them into a single model: the Cattell-Horn-Carroll (CHC) model of intelligence. This was later refined by McGrew and Flanagan (1998) as well as Flanagan et al. (2000). Beginning with ten broad cognitive abilities, this model is constantly revised. Schneider and McGrew (2012) summarized the addition of six broad abilities: general (domain-specific) knowledge, tactile abilities, psychomotor abilities, psychomotor speed, kinesthetic abilities, and olfactory abilities. The most recent CHC revision, Schneider and McGrew (2018), made a few more changes. For instance, short-term memory was renamed WM capacity, long-term storage and retrieval was split into two separate broad abilities, and emotional intelligence was proposed as a new broad ability. Thus, the CHC model now has 18 broad abilities, for which Schneider and McGrew (2018) proposed at least five conceptual and functional groupings, excluding emotional intelligence: reasoning (Gf), acquired knowledge (Gc, domain-specific knowledge, reading/writing, quantitative knowledge), memory (WM capacity, learning efficiency, and retrieval fluency), speed (reaction/decision time, processing speed, psychomotor speed), and sensorimotor ability (visual, auditory, olfactory, tactile, kinesthetic, psychomotor ability).

Explanations of the g-factor

The different theorists building up to CHC theory disagree on the origin of the g-factor. Spearman (Hart & Spearman, 1912) speculated that the g-factor is a “common fund of energy” (pg. 79), one that describes a general ability to reason (Spearman, 1923, 1927). However, Spearman conceded that the g-factor need not be an ability at all, or even a psychological construct in its own right (Spearman, 1934). Cattell (1963, 1987) and Horn (1985) did not view the g-factor as a unitary psychological construct representing general intelligence. Instead, Cattell (1987) proposed investment theory: people use Gf to acquire new knowledge, which in turn develops Gc. The resulting Gf-Gc correlation produces the positive manifold. In contrast, consistent with his hierarchical model, Carroll (1993, 1998, 2003) believed that the evidence for the existence of a causal g-factor was clear, representing general intelligence.

The current CHC model takes a view similar to Carroll (1993), with the g-factor a causal entity representing general intelligence. However, this conception is not essential to their model, and they encourage readers to disregard it if they disagree (Schneider & McGrew, 2012). Other explanations for the g-factor have been put forward, most of which are compatible with the CHC model’s taxonomy of intelligence. At the most basic level, the g-factor is the combination of forces that cause the abilities within a person to be more similar than they would otherwise be expected to be (Jensen, 2000). This includes not only cognitive factors, but any force that can influence the entire brain or general performance, such as motivation (Duckworth et al., 2011) as well as health factors including diseases, injuries, pathogens, or malnutrition (Daniele & Ostuni, 2013). Factors such as socioeconomic status may make it more likely that a child will avoid such health risks or be exposed to positive influences on intelligence, enabling the development of greater cognitive ability (Schneider & McGrew, 2012, 2018). While parental income does indeed positively predict intelligence in children, this relationship is weak (Camara, 2009; Rindermann & Ceci, 2018). Further, even after controlling for children’s socioeconomic status, IQ remains a moderate-to-strong positive predictor of later life outcomes, including educational attainment and job performance (Kuncel & Hezlett, 2010; Murray, 1998, 2002).

Another strike against environmental influences, including socioeconomic status, as the root of the g-factor comes from familial studies. In a review by Bouchard and McGue (1981), the average correlation between the IQs of identical twins raised together was $r = .86$. This represents a benchmark in which genetics are identical and environments are, presumably, quite similar. In contrast, the average correlation for identical twins raised apart was $r = .72$, while for unrelated children raised together it was between $r = .34$ (adopted-adopted) and $r = .29$ (adopted-biological). This points to a dominant role for genetics, while still finding that the environment contributes. Indeed, on average, approximately 50% of one’s IQ can be explained by genetics (Chipuer et al., 1990; Devlin et al., 1997; Loehlin, 1989). However, genetics make more of a difference with age: the extent to which intelligence is explained by genetics is often as low as 20% for children, while it is often as high as 80% for adults, highlighting the greater role of genetics later in life (Bouchard, 2013; Deary et al., 2012; Plomin et al., 1994). Genetic effects on IQ may be amplified with age as people create unique environments to suit their natural intellectual propensities (Briley & Tucker-Drob, 2013; Plomin, 1986).

A number of cognitive theories have been proposed for the basis of the g-factor (Carroll, 1993). One of the first was Thomson’s (1916) sampling theory, which argued that different cognitive tests “sample” different cognitive abilities, with some general abilities more important to a particular test than others. Some of these general abilities may be relevant to many tests, causing them to be positively correlated. Across all tests, the overlapping demands lead to a

positive manifold, one that does not require a singular ability underlying the g-factor. Alternatively, singular abilities have been proposed as the basis of the g-factor: Jensen (1998) argued that the g-factor could be largely based on the speed of mental operations, while Eysenck (1998) said it was the efficiency of neural transmission. However, the evidence for these single-ability theories is weak. For instance, the correlation between IQ and mean reaction time is generally weak-to-moderate (Deary, 2001; Detterman, 1987) and driven by a lack of slow responses (e.g., due to inattention) rather than fast responses (Coyle, 2003; Larson & Alderton, 1990). In addition, Kranzler and Jensen (1991, 1993) as well as Detterman (1994, 2000) demonstrated statistically that the g-factor likely arises from a number of independent cognitive processes (consistent with sampling theory), rather than a single process.

Recently, a new theory of the g-factor has been proposed that is based on and extends Thomson's (1916) sampling theory: Kovacs and Conway's (2016) process overlap theory (POT). POT states that all cognitive tests require a combination of domain-general cognitive abilities (useful for most or all tests) and domain-specific cognitive abilities (useful for that or similar tests). Since all tests rely to some extent on domain-general abilities, test performance is correlated, giving rise to the positive manifold and the g-factor. However, because each test also requires domain-specific abilities, their correlation with other tests is not perfect. This explains why some broad abilities load more strongly onto the g-factor than others: those that require more domain-general and less domain-specific processing share more variance with the g-factor, resulting in a stronger loading. For instance, Gf correlates almost perfectly with the g-factor (Gustafsson, 1984; Matzke et al., 2010), likely because it is a relatively pure assessment of domain-general processing abilities without domain-specific dilution. In POT, domain-general resources serve as a bottleneck for cognitive performance (cf. Thomson, 1916): a person may have impressive domain-specific abilities that are suited to a particular test, but if their domain-general abilities are lacking, their test performance will be severely limited.

In POT, the g-factor is thus caused by the domain-general resources shared by most or all tests (Kovacs & Conway, 2016). POT proposes that these domain-general resources are likely an assortment of executive functions, such as goal maintenance and inhibitory control. Importantly, POT does not state that these cognitive resources are synonymous with the g-factor. Instead, psychological constructs such as goal maintenance, shared across tests, lead to a positive manifold, which in turn is captured via the psychometric construct of the g-factor. This reflects the causal structure of POT, which places broad cognitive abilities at its core. It argues that these broad abilities are the most “real” constructs, which in turn inform performance on narrow abilities (below them in the hierarchy) and define the g-factor (above them in the hierarchy). Kovacs and Conway (2016) liken the g-factor to socioeconomic status in this sense, which predicts many favourable life outcomes. It is not socioeconomic status per se causing these outcomes, but rather the collection of personal conditions that together define socioeconomic status (e.g., wealth, education). However, it is debated whether broad abilities (such as Gf) are truly more real than the g-factor, as POT argues (Burgoyne et al., 2022).

Burgoyne et al. (2022) generally agreed with POT, but argued that the g-factor representing the positive manifold may be as real a construct as broad cognitive abilities such as Gf. As such, they were relatively comfortable associating the g-factor with specific domain-general cognitive resources, ones that explain the correlation between broad abilities. In particular, Burgoyne et al. (2022) proposed that attention control may underlie the g-factor. Attention control supports two complimentary processes: maintenance (keeping relevant

information in an active and accessible state) and disengagement (removing irrelevant information from active processing; Burgoyne et al., 2022; Burgoyne & Engle, 2020; Shipstead et al., 2016). Being relevant to most tasks, attention control is a plausible candidate for a domain-general cognitive function underlying the g-factor. To assess this, Burgoyne et al. (2022) reanalyzed the data of Tsukahara et al. (2020) and Draheim et al. (2022). First, using measures of attention control, Gf, WM capacity, and auditory discrimination ability, they found a positive manifold, described by a g-factor. Second, the attention control factor loaded onto the g-factor stronger than any other factor included (.98, compared to .81 for Gf). Third and finally, in a model where attention control stood in for the g-factor, there were either no or significantly reduced residual correlations between the other factors, suggesting that attention control largely explains their positive manifold. However, some cognitive abilities were not included in these data and may not be as well explained by attention control, such as Gc.

Neural Basis of the g-factor

The g-factor does not appear to have a single correlate in the brain (Kovacs & Conway, 2016), or “neuro-g” (Haier et al., 2009). Rather, the g-factor is associated with a diverse set of brain regions, no one of which may be consistently activated across all cognitive tasks (Jung & Haier, 2007; Kievit et al., 2012). One partial exception to this, however, was Román et al. (2014), which related participants’ Gf, Gc, and spatial intelligence to grey matter correlates. They found that, as you move up the intelligence hierarchy from specific tests to broad abilities to the g-factor, the number of grey matter correlates becomes smaller and more frontal. A higher g-factor was associated with greater grey matter volume and cortical surface area of the right middle frontal gyrus. However, being correlational, this does not demonstrate that the middle frontal gyrus is necessary for tests of these cognitive abilities, only that its anatomy predicts performance. For Gc in particular, it could be the capacity to acquire knowledge, rather than the retrieval of that knowledge, that correlates with middle frontal gyrus anatomy. This acquisition capacity may be determined by abilities apart from Gc (Cattell, 1987). The uniqueness of Gc is well illustrated by cases dissociating Gf and Gc. For instance, Gf measures have stronger correlates in the prefrontal cortex than Gc, while Gc has stronger correlates in the temporal lobes than Gf (Choi et al., 2008; Colom et al., 2009). Further, frontal damage typically impairs Gf but leaves Gc intact (Duncan et al., 1995, 1996; Hebb, 1942), while Gf declines with age despite Gc remaining similar or increasing (Ackerman, 1996; McArdle et al., 2000).

More success has been achieved when trying to localize specific forms of intelligence, in particular Gf. One candidate for the neural basis of Gf is the multiple-demand (MD) system (Duncan, 2010). Duncan and Owen (2000), in a review of prior neuroimaging findings, first revealed a network associated with a diverse range of cognitive functions, including WM, episodic memory, response selection, attention control, and problem solving. This MD system extends over broad prefrontal and parietal cortical regions, including areas in and around the middle frontal gyrus, posterior inferior frontal sulcus, anterior insula and adjacent frontal operculum, pre-supplementary motor area and adjacent anterior cingulate, as well as the intraparietal sulcus (Duncan, 2010; Duncan & Owen, 2000). An integration of three meta-analyses by Müller et al. (2015) confirmed that the MD system was activated by tasks involving WM (Rottschy et al., 2012), attention (Langner & Eickhoff, 2013), and inhibition (Cieslik et al., 2015). Fedorenko et al. (2013), using seven diverse cognitively demanding tasks, demonstrated that overlapping activation is present at the individual level and is not merely an artefact of

smoothing. Activation of the MD system appears to have a causal role in cognitive functioning, rather than being a general marker of task difficulty (Cope et al., 2022).

The MD system has been directly linked to Gf. Duncan and Owen (2000) scanned participants as they completed high Gf-loading tasks (i.e., verbal, spatial, and circles tasks) as well as low Gf-loading tasks, designed to be similar but lacking a problem-solving component. Contrasting these two conditions revealed activation of this MD system (see also Bishop et al., 2008; Prabhakaran et al., 1997). Gray et al. (2003) further demonstrated that participants with higher Gf, while completing a WM task, had greater event-related neural activation of this network. Consistent with these findings, Woolgar et al. (2010) found that the extent of damage to frontal or parietal MD regions predicted Gf loss, while this was not the case for temporal damage. Later, Woolgar et al. (2018) expanded on this, finding that lesions weighted against a probabilistic activation map for the MD system, but not the higher-level language processing system, predicted the extent of Gf deficit. The opposite pattern was found for verbal fluency deficits, demonstrating that the MD and language processing systems are distinct. Camilleri et al. (2018) used meta-analytic connectivity modeling to identify what they described as the (frontal) “core” MD system: the middle frontal gyrus, inferior frontal sulcus (extending into the posterior inferior frontal gyrus), pre-supplementary motor area and anterior cingulate, as well as anterior insula. These regions may serve as cognitive managers, recruiting an “extended” MD system (e.g., inferior parietal sulcus, inferior frontal junction, pre-motor cortex) as needed based on specific demands. Duncan et al. (2000) agreed that the g-factor may result, at least in part, from the general attentional integration functions performed by the MD system.

Cognition and SIN

In the previous section, I discussed the basis of the g-factor as well as the structure of intelligence. All cognitive tests are positively correlated with one another, with this covariance captured by the g-factor. The CHC model places the g-factor at the top of a hierarchy with as many as 18 broad cognitive abilities below it. POT argues that the g-factor arises due to domain-general cognitive resources—perhaps attention control—that influence performance on all cognitive tests. With the nature and structure of intelligence in mind, we will now consider the specific cognitive abilities that have been shown to support SIN performance.

Cognitive Abilities Associated with SIN

Which cognitive abilities are relevant to SIN perception? This was the question asked by Akeroyd (2008), the first review of the subject. It reviewed 19 studies that related cognitive ability with SIN performance (one additional study has been retracted). The cognitive measures considered were diverse, including general ability such as scholarship achievement and IQ tests, as well as specific abilities such as WM. The vast majority of studies tested older adults, usually with hearing loss and often with hearing aids. All 19 studies but one (Surprenant & Watson, 2001) found some relationship between cognition and SIN. The effect of cognition may have varied by stimulus type, with most cognition-SIN correlations reported using sentences and modulated noise (Gatehouse et al., 2003; Lunner & Sundewall-Thorén, 2007). Cognition generally explained less variance in SIN performance than did hearing loss, in particular high-frequency hearing loss, consistent with prior work (Van Rooij & Plomp, 1990). Hearing loss played a larger role than cognition in eight studies (Humes et al., 1994), was comparable in three (George et al., 2007), and played a lesser role in one (Rudner et al., 2008).

Akeroyd (2008) argued that WM tests most consistently predicted SIN, in particular the Reading Span (RSpan; Foo et al., 2007; Lunner, 2003; Rudner et al., 2008). The RSpan was one of the first popularized measures of WM, designed by Daneman and Carpenter (1980) and later modified by Baddeley (1985) into its most widely used form (Besser et al., 2013). This task involves reading aloud a series of sentences, judging their plausibility, and being asked to recall the final words of each sentence at the end of the sentence list. In the similar Listening Span (LSpan), sentences are spoken aloud rather than read (Daneman & Carpenter, 1980). These are examples of “complex span” tasks, designed to tap into both the storage and processing functions of WM (Conway et al., 2005). This is accomplished by interleaving a memory storage task with a secondary processing task, therefore requiring access to information in the face of concurrent demands. In one RSpan study, Rudner et al. (2008) tested 80 older adults with hearing loss wearing hearing aids, who listened to sentences in static or modulated noise and with different hearing aid compression types. In all conditions, performance on the RSpan correlated with SRT in noise, while age and auditory factors were not always significant.

Despite Akeroyd’s conclusion that the RSpan was most related to SIN, his review pointed to only three (currently published) studies reporting a correlation between the RSpan and SIN performance (Foo et al., 2007; Lunner, 2003; Rudner et al., 2008). Further, general cognitive assessments, such as IQ tests and derived factors, also appeared quite effective in predicting SIN performance (Humes, 2002; Humes et al., 1994, 2007). For instance, Humes (2002) tested 171 older adults with hearing loss, who listened to syllables and sentences in quiet and babble. SIN performance was best predicted by hearing loss, but two cognitive factors, “non-verbal IQ and aging” as well as “verbal IQ,” both contributed as well. For most other studies using general cognitive predictors, a WM factor was included but did not predict SIN performance as effectively as other factors, such as performance IQ (Humes et al., 1994) and perceptual organization (Humes et al., 2007). Other tasks often predicted SIN performance as well, such as visual text reception tasks (George et al., 2007; Zekveld et al., 2007). Even tasks labelled as “miscellaneous,” such as rhyme judgement tasks, were surprisingly effective, despite their dissimilarity from SIN tasks (Lunner, 2003; Van Rooij & Plomp, 1990).

Two reviews later cast further doubt on the RSpan as the ideal predictor of SIN performance. Besser et al. (2013) reviewed 21 studies, including a range of age groups and hearing statuses, in which SRT in noise was measured as well as the RSpan/LSpan. The authors argued that these complex WM span tasks were able to predict SRT in noise, at least under certain circumstances: when speech was presented against speech maskers, and in particular when participants were older or had hearing loss (e.g., Desjardins & Doherty, 2013; Ellis & Munro, 2013). Shortly after, Füllgrabe and Rosen (2016b) conducted a meta-analysis with a similar scope, focusing on 19 studies (mostly of younger adults) to implement the RSpan. Surprisingly, RSpan did not predict SIN performance overall, or in younger adults, where it only explained less than 2% of the variance (e.g., Banks et al., 2015; Zekveld et al., 2014). Not enough older adult studies were included for a meta-analysis of that age group alone. However, the largest study in the meta-analysis (by the same authors), Füllgrabe and Rosen (2016a), found that RSpan predicted SIN performance for older but not younger adults.

The most recent meta-analysis assessing the role of cognition in SIN came from Dryden et al. (2017). They reviewed 25 papers that related various cognitive abilities to SIN performance in both younger and older adults. Across all studies and cognitive measures, the correlation between cognition and SIN performance was $r = .31$, which did not differ noticeably by hearing

status or the stimuli used. However, different cognitive abilities correlated differently with SIN performance. All cognitive abilities that could be analyzed correlated with SIN performance except for Gc. The significant predictors included episodic memory ($r = .26$; e.g., Anderson et al., 2013), WM ($r = .28$; e.g., Gordon-Salant & Cole, 2016), inhibitory control ($r = .34$; e.g., Veneman et al., 2013), and—strongest of all—processing speed ($r = .39$; e.g., Zekveld et al., 2011). Unlike Gc, there were not enough studies measuring attention or Gf to analyze their relationships with SIN performance. The authors noted the striking consistency of the relationship between cognitive measures and SIN, with all abilities seemingly related. They describe $r \approx .3$ as the “magic number” connecting these faculties (pg. 17).

Although Dryden et al.'s (2017) meta-analysis could not analyze the effect of Gf, a small number of studies conducted by that time—and a great many since—point to its association with SIN performance (see Marsja et al., 2022). These studies most often use matrix reasoning tasks, among the most widespread of Gf tasks (Boebinger et al., 2015; Dahlgren, 2020; Mattingly et al., 2018; O'Neill et al., 2019; Van Hedger et al., in preparation; but see Tamati et al., 2013). In this task, participants are presented with a grid of figures, one of which is missing, and must choose a figure that completes the pattern (Raven, 1936). For instance, Mattingly et al. (2018) showed that higher matrix reasoning scores were associated with better SIN performance in participants using cochlear implants as well as controls with normal hearing. More recently, a study from my lab, Van Hedger et al. (in preparation), had 89 participants with normal hearing complete a matrix reasoning task and a series of WM tasks. Matrix reasoning score, once again, predicted listening performance in noise as well as a range of other acoustic challenges (e.g., time-compressed speech, noise-vocoded speech), even more so than WM capacity. Indeed, a relative importance analysis demonstrated that matrix reasoning score explained more variance in SIN performance than WM measures. Other Gf measures, such as logical reasoning tasks, have also been shown to positively predict SIN performance (Meister et al., 2013; Moore et al., 2014).

The Role of General Cognitive Ability

Reconciling the above research is difficult, although a few general conclusions can be drawn. WM tests such as the RSpan may predict SIN performance, especially in older adults and perhaps using specific stimuli, such as sentences presented against more complex maskers (Akeroyd, 2008; Besser et al., 2013; Füllgrabe & Rosen, 2016b). However, this is by no means the only cognitive ability (or test) to predict SIN performance. A wide variety of others have proven to be similarly effective, such as Gf, processing speed, and inhibitory control, many of which are not obviously connected to a listener's ability to understand SIN (Akeroyd, 2008; Dryden et al., 2017; Marsja et al., 2022). Indeed, even to the extent that the RSpan correlates with SIN performance, this does not necessarily point exclusively to WM (Dryden et al., 2017; Surprenant, & Neath, 2009). Rather, the RSpan requires a collection of abilities beyond WM, such as language comprehension skills (Schwering & MacDonald, 2020).

At least three explanations exist for the diversity of cognitive tasks predicting SIN performance. First, and most commonly argued, these correlations have been explained in causal terms: higher ability in each of these domains directly supports SIN performance. For instance, after arriving at their so-called “magic number” of $r \approx .3$ connecting cognition and SIN performance, Dryden et al. (2017) speculated as to how each tested ability may support SIN perception. This explanation may be true to some extent, with a wide range of specific abilities playing some role. It may be the unique variance of these abilities, rather than what they share

with others, that predicts and supports SIN performance. However, Heinrich (2021) argued that the field needs to move beyond the interpretation of singular abilities, such as WM. Instead, she suggested that cognitive hearing science incorporate modern cognitive theories to better understand how various abilities relate to each other and SIN performance. This should include latent constructs rather than single tests, and the shared variance between them.

With this in mind, the second explanation is that one or a small subset of cognitive abilities is causally supporting SIN performance, with all other abilities merely correlated with that central ability. This was considered by Marsja et al. (2022), arguing that Gf may be correlated with SIN performance only due to its shared variance with WM. A moderate-to-strong positive correlation is often observed between WM and Gf (e.g., Kyllonen & Christal, 1990), which is greater than $r = .7$ at the latent variable level (Kane et al., 2005). Engle et al. (1999) demonstrated that WM capacity predicted Gf even when controlling for memory storage ability, but storage ability did not predict Gf when controlling for WM capacity. Thus, the processing component of WM, rather than storage, likely explains its positive correlation with Gf (but see Unsworth et al., 2014). According to executive attention theory, attention control underlies both of these abilities and accounts for their association (Engle, 2002; Engle & Kane, 2003). In particular, Gf may primarily rely on disengagement, while WM processing may rely on maintenance—both supported by attention control (Shipstead et al., 2016). Given this close association between Gf and WM, either ability may support SIN performance.

The third and final explanation for the consistent cognition-SIN link is perhaps the most parsimonious one. A vast array of cognitive abilities may correlate with SIN performance not because any of them is supporting it directly, but because they are all positively correlated with general intelligence. Thus, general intelligence, or whatever cognitive and other factors underlie it, may be supporting SIN performance. This possibility has previously been noted, including by Boebinger et al. (2015), which suggested that general cognitive ability be considered in future studies of SIN perception. In this scenario, attention control or other domain-general executive processes may be supporting not only the vast majority of cognitive abilities, but also SIN performance. This would be consistent with the most recent version of the CHC model. While models of intelligence have long included an auditory processing ability (Horn, 1965, 1968), even Schneider and McGrew (2012) limited the definition to nonverbal tasks. Considering the work of Conzelmann and Süß (2015), Schneider and McGrew's (2018) revision included a speech category within auditory processing. This includes the narrow abilities of phonetic coding, speech sound discrimination, and resistance to auditory stimulus distortion. The last of these abilities, crucially, is defined as “the ability to hear words or extended speech passages correctly under conditions of distortion or background noise” (pg. 132).

Based on this definition, it should be no surprise that SIN performance is correlated with many cognitive abilities, as they all share variance with one another, based on their support from the domain-general cognitive abilities of general intelligence. Tsukahara et al. (2020) demonstrated that attention control fully mediates the relationship between general intelligence and auditory discrimination that was first suggested by Spearman (1904). As we saw above, Burgoyne et al. (2022), using the same data, also showed that when attention control stands in for the g-factor, it eliminated all positive correlations between auditory discrimination and other broad cognitive abilities. We can thus reframe the correlation between SIN performance and other cognitive abilities as a part of the positive manifold, which describes how all tests, including SIN tests, covary positively. To explain the positive manifold, we do not attempt to

explain how each ability is supported by each other. Rather, we appeal to the domain-general factors underlying all tests. The same can, and perhaps should, be done here. The best explanation for the link between cognition and SIN performance may be that attention control and other resources support them all. Consistent with this view, the MD system, supporting the attentional functions of intelligence, is activated by SIN perception and other listening challenges (Eckert et al., 2009; Ritz et al., 2022; Rovetti et al., in preparation; Wild et al., 2012). For instance, in another study from my lab, Rovetti et al. (in preparation), 24 participants listened to speech with and without background noise and semantically ambiguous words. Both at the group level and individual level, voxels within the left anterior cingulate cortex and anterior insula (components of the MD system) responded to SIN and semantic ambiguity.

A few studies since Akeroyd's (2008) review have investigated the role of general cognitive ability in SIN perception. Most SIN studies employing a battery of cognitive measures use factor analysis to reduce them, which generally leads to the formation of more than one cognition factor. One exception was Heinrich et al. (2015), which had 44 middle-aged and older adults with mild hearing loss complete a series of cognitive tests. All tests were best grouped into a “general cognition” factor, which predicted SIN performance for sentences (but not for words) over and above audiometric hearing loss. A two-factor solution for cognition, while not quite as effective, revealed that a factor including attention and reasoning ability was more predictive of SIN performance than was a WM factor. A number of studies have also used canonical correlation to provide indirect evidence for an association between SIN performance and performance on a collection of cognitive tasks, often including measures of general cognitive ability (Jerger et al., 1991; Van Rooij et al., 1989; Van Rooij & Plomp, 1990). Finally, a handful of studies measuring the perception of degraded speech (including but not limited to SIN) have included IQ tests and calculated full-scale IQ as intended (Humes, 2005; Vaughan et al., 2008). For instance, Vaughan et al. (2008) had 225 middle-aged and older adults complete a cognitive battery that included an IQ test. Full-scale IQ as well as verbal IQ scores were found to be positively correlated with the recognition of time-compressed speech.

Cognitive Testing in Audiology

In the previous section, I discussed the specific cognitive abilities that have been shown to predict SIN performance. Although WM tests such as the RSpan can predict SIN performance, so do most other cognitive assessments, including IQ tests. I propose that the domain-general cognitive resources that define general intelligence may be supporting SIN performance as a narrow cognitive ability, as they do all other cognitive abilities. Having discussed the cognitive contributions to SIN performance, I will now shift focus to the methods that audiologists have used to test cognition, including the shortcomings of these methods.

Cognitive Screenings

Recently, there has been a push toward the measurement of cognitive ability in audiological practice (Broome et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2022; Humes, 2021; Pichora-Fuller, 2008; Kricos, 2006; Weinstein, 2015). This is due to not only the known link between cognition and SIN performance, but also an association between hearing loss and cognitive decline (see Wayne & Johnsrude, 2015). For instance, elevated pure-tone thresholds are present in over 90% of those with dementia (Gold et al., 1996), a higher rate than age-matched controls (Uhlmann et al., 1989). Because aging causes both sensory and cognitive decline, it is difficult to determine the direction of causation here. Recently, however, stronger evidence has been presented in

favour of a causal pathway from sensory decline to cognitive decline (Lindenberger & Baltes, 1994; Schneider & Pichora-Fuller, 2000). Glick and Sharma (2020) fitted hearing aids to older adults with untreated hearing loss. Six months later, they ceased exhibiting compensatory neural activation present at baseline, and their SIN performance and cognitive scores improved. Preliminary results from Lin et al. (2023) offered the most direct evidence, which randomly assigned older adults with hearing loss to either receive hearing aids or not. In a subgroup at greater risk of developing dementia, the participants given hearing aids were 48% less likely to have developed cognitive decline when assessed at a three-year follow-up.

A survey in the United Kingdom by Broome et al. (2023) found that patients' attitudes on cognitive testing in audiology clinics is generally positive, with 92% of respondents willing to be tested cognitively. This is similar to older adults' willingness to be cognitively tested more generally (Raymond et al., 2020; Wong & Jacova, 2018). Most respondents were aware of the cognition-hearing link and willing for this reason, provided it was executed properly. In particular, respondents wanted these tests to be well justified (e.g., guiding future care), conducted by qualified professionals, in an appropriate format (e.g., without an emphasis on auditory items), and they wanted to be able to ask questions and discuss their results. Despite its importance and the willingness of patients, another survey in the United States by Raymond et al. (2020) found that only about 22% of American audiologists used any form of cognitive testing. This is perhaps because, as reported by Black and Souza (2020), only 17% of American audiologists report being trained to administer cognitive assessments in their graduate studies, although this number rises to 42% when considering continuing education.

Audiologists are divided on which cognitive assessment to use. Raymond et al. (2020) found that 42% of American audiologists (and other hearing professionals) would use the Mini Mental State Exam (MMSE; Folstein et al., 1975), while 20% would use the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA; Nasreddine et al., 2005). Other screenings include the Mini-Cog (Borson et al., 2000), an even shorter assessment; as well as the Clock Drawing Task (Shulman et al., 1986), an effective single-item screening (Beck et al., 2016; Souza, 2019). In audiology, cognitive testing almost always takes the form of such cognitive screenings. These screenings are generally very fast (less than 15 mins) and easy to administer, making them appealing for audiologists (Cordell et al., 2013; Shen et al., 2016). They are designed with cut-off scores to indicate whether a person is more likely to have a condition compared to a reference group (Cullen et al., 2007), thus being a candidate for further testing (Morley et al., 2015).

The MMSE and the MoCA vary slightly in their uses. The MMSE is designed to screen for dementia, while the MoCA screens for mild cognitive impairment (MCI)—a less severe condition in which daily functioning is largely preserved (Petersen, 2004). These screenings are both effective at detecting their respective conditions. For instance, the MoCA has a sensitivity to MCI of 90% and a specificity of 87%. Of these two screenings, the MoCA, being designed to detect MCI, is more sensitive to slight declines in cognitive ability than the MMSE (Hoops et al., 2009; Roalf et al., 2013). Indeed, the MoCA is less prone to ceiling effects than the MMSE, exhibiting a wider range of scores from similar populations (Jia et al., 2021; Tumas et al., 2016). For these and other reasons, Humes (2021) advocated for the use of the MoCA by audiologists, rather than the MMSE. The MoCA has even been found to correlate with SIN performance in some cases (Mukari et al., 2020; Yiannos et al., 2023; Zhan et al., 2018).

Limitations of Current Practices

Despite the increasing popularity of cognitive screenings among audiologists, these tests are severely limited. Most importantly, screenings are designed to detect cases of diminished cognitive ability using cut-off scores, classifying whether people may have normal cognition or not (Roebuck-Spencer et al., 2017). They are not designed to provide a comprehensive or continuous assessment of cognitive ability—the form of assessment that would be more predictive of SIN performance. Humes (2020) found that while MoCA score does predict IQ score in older adults with a wide range of hearing abilities, they only exhibit a moderate positive correlation. The MoCA cannot estimate IQ score within 10 points for 40% of older adult patients (compared to a standard deviation of 15 points) and it cannot differentiate those with normal intelligence from those with above-average intelligence (Sugarman & Axelrod, 2014), let alone in a particular cognitive domain (Moafmashhadi & Koski, 2013). This limitation is reflected in the current use of cognitive screenings by audiologists, who generally only administer them to patients showing greater risk of diminished cognitive ability (e.g., Beck et al., 2016; Remensnyder, 2012; Shen et al., 2016; Souza, 2019). While these selective screening practices could identify people at the greatest risk of cognition-related SIN deficits, it ignores important variability in the normal-to-high range of cognitive ability (Souza, 2019).

To mitigate this problem, more thorough cognitive testing would be needed, capable of capturing the full spectrum of cognitive abilities. At present, this form of testing is exceedingly rare in audiological practice. Beyond the lab setting, private companies, such as Cognivue, Cogstate, and NeuroTrax have put forward computerized assessments of cognition, ones that appear to have the potential to be more precise in their findings. However, these too have been branded as substitutes for cognitive screenings such as the MoCA. For instance, Cognivue's own research suggests that it performs comparably to the MoCA (Cahn-Hidalgo et al., 2020; Ma & Cahn-Hidalgo, 2021), although external research suggests that more evidence is needed to support its effectiveness (Rose et al., 2021). Nonetheless, some audiologists have reported effectively using cognitive screenings such as Cognivue to inform treatment (Davis, 2021). The RSpan has also been implemented by a small number of audiologists, although, once again, the focus is generally on detecting those with below-average performance (Souza, 2019). Further, audiologists report that patients do not enjoy the RSpan (Johnsrude, personal communication). These limitations highlight the need for a more complete, continuous measure of general cognitive ability (including the normal and above-average range of ability).

Designing a Cognitive Assessment for Audiology

In the previous section, I discuss the cognitive measures that have been employed by audiologists and their limitations. Cognitive screening measures, such as the MMSE and the MoCA, are most commonly used. However, these are designed to detect cases of cognitive impairment, not assess cognitive ability. A need thus exists for a measure of cognitive ability for audiologists that can better capture patients' cognitive profile. Given this need, I will now consider how such a general cognitive assessment should be designed.

Why Measure General Cognitive Ability?

Even once it is decided to test cognitive ability, one may ask why it is necessary to use what is essentially an IQ test, rather than a test of WM or other cognitive abilities. Most importantly, as I have argued above, the domain-general cognitive abilities underlying the positive manifold may support SIN performance as well. If this proves to be true, measuring IQ would be the most effective and direct way to assess patients' cognitive capabilities as they relate

to SIN performance. Practical benefits also support the measurement of general cognitive ability. A measure of general cognitive ability would be the simplest option, leading to a singular cognitive variable that would be easier for audiologists to interpret and apply than an assortment of cognitive measures. In addition, measuring general cognitive ability is simpler than measuring many specific cognitive abilities. Approximating the g-factor requires only a few diverse cognitive tasks, whereas measuring even two specific cognitive abilities, such as WM and processing speed, would ideally involve a number of tests for each so that latent variables could be extracted. Finally, a more general assessment would still allow for the specific abilities tested, such as WM, to be roughly approximately, even if not the test's intention.

Abbreviated Tests of Cognitive Ability

For audiologists to implement cognitive testing, the assessment would best meet specific criteria. Some of these criteria were discussed above, such as the potential to capture a wide range of cognitive abilities, including normal and above-average cognition (in contrast to screenings). However, other features must also be prioritized. First, the assessment must be time-efficient. A typical intelligence test, such as the WAIS-IV, may take up to two hours to complete (Abdelhamid et al., 2021). American audiologists typically have more time to spend with their patients (often an hour for initial appointments) than do general practitioners (Kochkin, 2010). This makes audiologists well-suited to assess cognitive ability (Davis, 2021). Nonetheless, their time is still rather limited. An assessment completed by all patients would ideally take no more than 20 minutes. This would only allow for a handful of cognitive tests.

Abbreviated IQ tests have previously been developed. For instance, Kaufman's tetrad (Kaufman et al., 1991) is an assessment, composed of four subtests of the WAIS, that takes approximately 20 minutes. These subtests are Arithmetic, Similarities, Picture Completion, and the Digit Symbol Substitution Test (DSST). Despite its much shorter duration, in the standardization sample of the WAIS-III, full-scale IQ from the WAIS-III exhibited a correlation of .90 with full-scale IQ derived from Kaufman's tetrad. A more recent abbreviated IQ test is the Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence—Second Edition (WASI-II; Wechsler, 2011). This assessment, again with subtests from the WAIS, takes 30 minutes for a four-subtest form or 15 minutes for a two-subtest form. The longer version includes Similarities, Vocabulary, Block Design, and Matrix Reasoning, while the shorter version includes only Vocabulary and Matrix Reasoning. The standardization sample exhibited a correlation of .92 between WAIS-III full-scale IQ and WASI four-subtest full-scale IQ, decreasing to .87 for the WASI two-subtest full-scale IQ. Kaufman's tetrad and the WASI are both valid and reliable, although their correlation with full-length IQ tests is weaker in clinical samples (Axelrod, 2002).

Even single-test assessments have been used to approximate IQ, in particular Raven's Progressive Matrices (RPM; Raven, 1936), a matrix reasoning task measuring Gf. RPM score correlates at approximately $r = .7$ with the g-factor (DeYoung et al., 2005; Rogers et al., 1994), and it is often stated that such matrix reasoning tasks are nearly a pure measure of the g-factor (Jensen, 1980; Spearman, 1946). However, Gignac (2015) cautioned against this use of RPM, demonstrating that it only shares about 50% of its variance with the g-factor, with 10% attributable to Gf and 25% to test-specific factors. Indeed, any single-item assessment of intelligence is not advisable in research or clinically (Haier et al., 2009). Instead, Gignac (2015) proposed an assessment that includes the following four subtests of the WAIS: Similarities, Digit Span Backward, Matrix Reasoning, and DSST. This assessment would take only approximately

14 minutes to complete and would have a correlation with the g-factor of .93, nominally higher than all of the abbreviated IQ tests discussed above (Gignac, 2015).

Non-Auditory and Non-Verbal Tests of Cognitive Ability

Second, to avoid the influence of hearing loss, the tests included should be non-auditory and, as much as possible, non-verbal. This will not only ensure that people with hearing loss are accurately assessed, but also enable the wide use of this assessment around the world, with only the instructions needing to be translated into other languages (Broome et al., 2023; Wayne & Johnsrude, 2015). Hearing loss disadvantages those taking cognitive tests with auditory components. For instance, Jorgensen et al. (2016) found that normal-hearing participants who were given simulated hearing loss performed worse on the MMSE than those without simulated hearing loss. To remedy this, scoring modifications have been proposed. Dupuis et al. (2015) found that more people with hearing loss passed the MoCA when auditory items were removed. However, Al-Yawer et al. (2019), when removing auditory subtests, found that this reduced the sensitivity and specificity of the MoCA to detecting MCI. Taking a step further, Dawes et al. (2019, 2023) created the MoCA-H, a version for people with hearing impairment. The authors found that, compared to the original MoCA, the MoCA-H had comparable sensitivity and specificity to dementia. However, they did not include a group diagnosed with MCI, the detection of which is meant to be one of the main strengths of the MoCA.

To avoid biases for certain groups, other IQ tests have tried to minimize the influence of language and culture. The WAIS-IV was normed on 2200 individuals between the ages of 16 and 90 (Wechsler, 2008). A problem is thus presented when IQ tests are applied to groups against which they were not normed. Even within a country, different cultural groups may perform better than others not necessarily due to genetic or environmental factors, but cultural factors (Helms, 1992). After all, intelligence—especially G_c —only makes sense in the context of one's culture, which determines what knowledge is valued (Sternberg & Grigorenko, 2014). This problem is exacerbated at the international level. As a result, international versions of the WAIS must be adapted to each culture and normed on a representative sample (e.g., García et al., 2003; Grégoire, 2004). However, this process is time-consuming. Alternatively, attempts have been made to design culture-reduced IQ tests, to the extent that this is possible. One early attempt was the Cattell Culture Fair Intelligence Test, which includes a series of non-verbal test, most involving identifying and completing visual patterns (Cattell, 1940). Other examples of culture-reduced tests include the Test of Nonverbal Abilities—Fourth Edition (Brown et al., 2010) as well as the Wechsler Nonverbal Scale of Ability (Wechsler & Naglieri, 2006), both of which are also ideal for patients with hearing impairments. These culture-reduced assessments generally neglect G_c , being the most culturally-specific of all broad cognitive abilities.

Selecting Cognitive Abilities to Measure

With the understanding that an IQ test for use by audiologists should be brief, non-auditory, and non-verbal, the structure of this assessment can be considered. Despite there being 18 broad cognitive abilities in the CHC model, not all are equally well established (Schneider & McGrew, 2018). For instance, the most recent version of the model states that all sensorimotor abilities apart from visual and auditory processing, as well as emotional intelligence, have “provisional” status. In contrast, approximately 10 broad abilities are supported by strong evidence (Carroll, 1993, 2003). The oldest and best established of these broad abilities are G_f

and Gc (Cattell, 1941; Cattell, 1943), followed by processing speed, WM, long-term storage and retrieval, visual processing, and auditory processing (Horn, 1965, 1968).

All of these broad cognitive abilities, apart from auditory processing—which is strangely neglected by almost all common IQ tests (Conzelmann & Süß, 2015)—are also the broad abilities most represented in general intelligence testing (McGrew, 2009). This includes the WAIS-IV, which includes index scores for concepts mapping onto processing speed, WM (both with the same names), Gc (Verbal Comprehension), as well as a factor serving as a combination of Gf and visual processing (Perceptual Reasoning; Grégoire, 2013). A factor analysis of the WAIS-IV by Benson et al. (2010) revealed that the five-factor solution of the CHC model, separating Perceptual Reasoning into Gf and visual processing, was more effective than the four-factor solution of the WAIS (see also Canivez & Kush, 2013). However, the inclusion of visual processing, as with auditory processing, could disadvantage those with hearing loss, since age causes losses to both of these senses (Campbell et al., 1999; Davis, 2021).

Gignac's (2015) proposed abbreviated IQ test had a structure consistent with this perspective above, including all WAIS-IV broad cognitive abilities except for visual processing. In particular, he measured Gf (Matrix Reasoning), Gc (Similarities), WM (Digit Span Backward), and processing speed (DSST). Following Gignac (2015), I tentatively recommend that a general intelligence test for use in audiology include a test for each of the following four broad abilities: Gf (e.g., RPM; Arthur & Day, 1994; Raven, 1936), Gc (e.g., years of education and occupational skill level; Ceci, 1991; Hagemann-von Arx et al., 2016), WM capacity (e.g., Symmetry Span; Conway et al., 2005; Unsworth et al., 2009), and processing speed (e.g., DSST; McLeod et al., 1982; Wechsler, 1955). This brief battery of non-auditory, non-verbal tests also effectively samples from each grouping of broad abilities, apart from sensorimotor: reasoning, acquired knowledge, memory, and speed (Schneider & McGrew, 2018).

Applying a Cognitive Assessment for Audiology

In the previous section, I discussed how a cognitive assessment for use in audiology should be designed. I propose that a brief, non-auditory, non-verbal assessment—one that provides an effective estimate of IQ—could sample the broad cognitive abilities of Gf, Gc, WM, and processing speed. Finally, I will discuss how such a cognitive assessment could be used by audiologists to inform the assessment and treatment of hearing loss.

Cognition and Audition Interact

Being tentative, the test battery proposed above will need research to support its effectiveness, both to measure the g-factor and aid audiologists. Nonetheless, it is worth considering how this assessment may be used. If cognitive testing is to be implemented, it should be considered only after assessments of audition, including pure-tone audiometry and suprathreshold tests such as the Audible Contrast Threshold Test. Moreover, the results of cognitive testing cannot be directly translated into an intervention. This is in contrast to pure-tone audiometry, where patients' audiograms can be used to fit a hearing aid to compensate for their unique profile of hearing loss. When it comes to cognition, there is little evidence that general cognitive abilities can be improved (e.g., trained) in a generalizable way (Owen et al., 2010; Simons et al., 2016). In any case, this is beyond the scope of audiology. As a result, the application of cognitive assessments will not be as straightforward.

Cognitive factors can compensate for signal degradation such as background noise or hearing loss, demonstrating that bottom-up and top-down processing trade off (Wingfield et al., 2005; Wingfield & Tun, 2007). Older adults with hearing loss may leverage not only their cognitive ability, as discussed above, but also contextual and other cues, which they rely upon more than younger adults with normal hearing (Pichora-Fuller, 2008; Pichora-Fuller et al., 1995; Pichora-Fuller & Singh, 2006). Indeed, cognitive ability predicts the extent to which listeners benefit from contextual information (Janse & Jesse, 2014; Zekveld et al., 2012). In addition, such cognitive differences may partially account for why, even among listeners with normal audiograms, some report poor SIN performance. Listening effort has often been invoked as an explanation for this phenomenon, as it may well be (Pichora-Fuller et al., 2016). However, it is possible that having higher cognitive ability affords more effortful processing, which may not be an option to those with lower ability (Herrmann & Johnsrude, 2020). As a result, listeners' cognition is best considered in combination with their hearing ability.

Who Should Be Cognitively Tested?

Audiologists must begin by deciding which patients should be cognitively tested. Because most cognitive testing in audiology is screening for MCI, it has generally been applied to only a select number of patients. Even for a relatively comprehensive cognitive assessment, this may be a reasonable approach. After all, cognitive testing may be best used in cases where poor SIN performance or some other deficit must be accounted for. Otherwise, this could be considered wasted resources. With this careful use in mind, Remensnyder (2012) proposed that a patient history be taken, with questions about memory, head injury, and depression. The decision to screen, they argued, should be informed by such questions. Shen et al. (2016) advocated for this same approach, while also emphasizing that audiologists watch for signs of cognitive or behavioural abnormalities in the clinic (e.g., missing appointments). Souza (2019) argued against universal screening, citing its impracticality and the high risk of MCI false positives. Instead, she suggested that only patients (or their families) reporting cognitive deficits be screened, or those in higher-risk groups (e.g., older adults). More specifically, Beck et al. (2016) pushed for the screening of all patients over the age of 70 with hearing difficulties.

Alternatively, arguments exist for cognitively testing almost all patients in audiology. After all, cognition and hearing are closely linked, and cognitive ability appears to affect SIN performance (at least to some extent) in all groups. As a result, if a patient is experiencing any concern that justifies an audiologist visit, the cognitive perspective may help address it. Cognitive testing may even be useful if a patient reports normal SIN performance. For instance, normal SIN performance may be achieved by leveraging cognitive ability (and listening effort) despite threshold or suprathreshold deficits. This could only be ascertained if cognition were assessed. Further, cognitive ability may not affect only SIN performance, but also pure-tone audiometry and other tasks that seem to be pure assessments of auditory functioning. For instance, Welch and Dawes (2007) reported that among children with hearing thresholds in the normal range, IQ score predicted pure-tone threshold. They argued that, although multiple factors may contribute to this, one of them is the psychological and cognitive requirements of hearing tests, including selective attention. This must be acknowledged for other auditory tests as well (Back et al., 2022). Universal cognitive testing would align with the recommendations of Davis (2021), who advocated for a non-verbal screening in all patients.

How Should Test Results Be Used?

The next decision faced by audiologists, after deciding to test a particular patient, is how to make use of their cognitive results. This includes how to score the test and which specific measures to use. Audiologists could aggregate the scores to calculate a full-scale IQ score. Raw (i.e., non-normed) scores may be most practical, since the absolute level of ability likely determines the level of SIN performance achieved. In addition, they could also use the scores from individual domains separately. The best decision may depend on what future research has to say regarding the roles of general and specific cognitive abilities in SIN perception. Further, Gc may prove to be a special case compared to other abilities. As mentioned above, it dissociates from other forms of intelligence both in the brain and as a function of age. As a result, a test of Gc may not reflect a patient's current abilities in the way that tests of the other cognitive domains would. This is especially true for older patients visiting an audiologist, who may be experiencing some cognitive decline. However, even if not included in the IQ calculation, Gc could still be a highly useful measure. For instance, with Gc largely preserved with age, it could reflect a person's peak intellectual functioning prior to any recent losses in other domains. A large difference between Gc and other scores, even if those other scores are in the normal range, could explain why a patient is reporting declines in their SIN performance.

When using test results, audiologists must also keep in mind what they can and cannot address. For cognitive tests, as with screenings, some level of functioning may be considered a sign of impairment worthy of further investigation. A number of researchers and audiologists have argued that, due to their extended time with patients, audiologists should act as gatekeepers assessing cognitive ability in patients, referring them to other medical professionals when needed (Shen et al., 2016). This effort may go in both directions, with memory clinics often encouraged to refer patients with possible hearing impairment to audiologists (McDonough et al., 2021). Beck et al. (2016) offered some recommendations for how to handle the referral process. Audiologists should emphasize the need for further testing rather than speculate, and they should have professionals ready to receive referrals in these cases. Within reasonable limits, the patient should be able to ask questions about the results and the process (Broome et al., 2023). Audiologists do not have to emphasize the specialization of the professional referred to (e.g., a psychologist), rather that they are simply taking a holistic approach by consulting others. Humanizing this professional may also help, such as by talking about how they know each other or their personality. Audiologists should also remind concerned patients that they are not defined by any impairment they may have, emphasizing that it can be managed.

In those without impaired cognition, how can cognitive results be useful? A few options are available in these cases. Davis (2021) has used score on the Cognivue screening to track changes over time and set target SIN performance levels. When patients fall short of those targets, training or educational interventions may be used. As mentioned, cognitive ability per se likely cannot be trained. However, some evidence supports certain forms of training to improve SIN performance. For instance, short-term musical training has found some success (Dubinsky et al., 2019; Worschech et al., 2021; Zendel et al., 2019). Online SIN training programs have also been designed, including the Listening and Communication Enhancement program (Sweetow & Henderson-Sabes, 2004) as well as the ReadMyQuips program (<http://sensesynergy.com>). These programs generally involve exercises that simulate real-world listening. Some evidence suggests that, unlike general cognitive training, SIN training can transfer to novel stimuli and environments (Ferguson et al., 2014). However, more evidence is needed to support these interventions and, if effective, integrate them into clinical practice. Alternatively, educational

interventions include counselling patients on the factors contributing to their hearing impairment and actions that can be taken to mitigate it (Souza, 2019). These may overlap with strategies recommended for hearing loss, given that cognition can compensate for such loss. For instance, listeners can make an effort to reduce the general cognitive load of their situation, rely more on visual cues, or encourage conversational partners to speak more slowly.

How Can Cognition Inform Hearing Aid Fitting?

Perhaps the most transformational intervention available to audiologists is the dispensation of hearing assistive devices, including hearing aids. Many have thus argued that patients' cognitive profiles should inform hearing aid fitting (Heinrich, 2021; Meister, 2017). As reviewed by Souza et al. (2015, 2019), the best type of hearing aid processing algorithm for a particular patient may be informed by cognitive abilities. Most research has been on wide dynamic range compression (WDRC), a form of processing that compresses speech by increasing the amplification of quiet sounds and reducing the amplification of loud sounds (Moore, 2008). In fast-acting WDRC, amplification is adjusted very quickly in response to changes in sound level. This allows adjustment at the level of individual phonemes, which may improve the audibility of speech, but compromises the perceived naturalness of the amplitude pattern (Jenstad & Souza, 2005; Stone & Moore, 2007). In contrast, slow-acting WDRC takes more time to adjust, meaning that speech sounds more natural but may not be as audible. Gatehouse et al. (2006) first demonstrated that those with lower WM capacity (as measured by letter- and digit-substitution tasks) performed better with slow-acting WDRC, while those with higher WM capacity benefitted more from fast-acting WDRC. This interaction has been consistently replicated both in lab participants (Foo et al., 2007; Lunner & Sundewall-Thorén, 2007; Ohlenforst et al., 2018) and clinical patients (Souza & Sirow, 2014).

WM capacity is argued to predict the benefit from fast-acting WDRC because this form of processing alters the signal more than slow-acting WDRC (Souza et al., 2015). According to the Ease of Language Understanding Model, WM serves SIN perception when a mismatch occurs between speech input and phonological and lexical long-term representations. As a result, high-alteration processing may tax WM. This could also explain why the benefit of fast-acting WDRC for high-WM listeners appears to be reduced with longer hearing aid use (Ng et al., 2014), since there is an opportunity for the listener to adjust their expectations. One limitation of this literature is that almost all studies investigating the association between cognitive abilities and hearing aid processing focus on WM (Humes, 2021). This presents a familiar problem: it is not clear if WM per se is predicting this benefit, or whether more general cognitive ability is responsible. Indeed, in one rare study to measure a different ability, participants with faster processing speed had greater benefit from fast-acting WDRC (Yumba, 2017).

Regardless of the cognitive ability involved, these results can inform how audiologists fit hearing aids. If patients are of higher cognitive ability (e.g., WM), they would likely benefit from fast-acting WDRC, whereas those with lower ability should use slow-acting WDRC. Further, other forms of processing should be emphasized for those with lower cognitive ability. For instance, digital noise reduction algorithms attempt to remove background noise while retaining speech (Bentler & Chiou, 2006). Unlike fast-acting WDRC, this should not greatly affect the naturalness of the signal unless aggressive (Souza, 2019). Digital noise reduction has been shown to not only increase speech intelligibility, but also reduce listening load and the need for compensatory resources (Fiedler et al., 2021; Reinten et al., 2021). Consistent with this, WM

capacity does not reliably predict the benefit from digital noise reduction (c.f. Arehart et al., 2013; Neher et al., 2014). Souza (2019) encouraged audiologists to use slow-acting WDRC and moderate digital noise reduction for patients with lower cognitive ability. Other technologies can be used to further reduce cognitive load, such as directional microphones, which pick up sound primarily from a single predetermined direction (Rumoshovsky, 1977).

Conclusions

In sum, despite SIN deficits being the most common patient complaint to audiologists, predicting SIN performance remains difficult. Pure-tone audiometry and suprathreshold tests allow for approximately half of the variance to be explained, with cognitive measures inching this up further. Nearly all cognitive abilities have been found to predict SIN performance. WM capacity is discussed the most in this context, although IQ as well as specific abilities such as processing speed and Gf can predict SIN performance to a similar extent. A number of explanations may account for this. As described by the positive manifold, all cognitive abilities positively correlate with one another, defining a g-factor. This positive manifold may result from domain-general cognitive abilities, such as attention control, that influence performance on all tasks—including SIN tasks. Thus, general cognitive ability may support and predict SIN performance more than any specific ability. With this in mind, I argued that a brief, non-auditory, non-verbal assessment of general cognitive ability should be commonplace in audiological practice. Such a test could sample the broad cognitive abilities of Gf, Gc, WM, and processing speed to arrive at a good approximation of general cognitive ability.

Going forward, many questions remain unanswered. First and foremost, more evidence is needed that general cognitive ability is supporting SIN performance. Proving this may be difficult. After all, all cognitive abilities are positively correlated with general cognitive ability. Nonetheless, it is achievable using methods such as structural equation modelling. In addition, the proposed four-item assessment will need to be finalized and validated for clinical use. Numerous practical concerns will need to be considered, such as the format of the test and the role of audiologists in administration. Despite my tentative suggestions above, the scoring of the test must also be settled, as well as who should be cognitively tested and how their results could be used to inform diagnosis and treatment (e.g., SIN training). This includes, potentially, the setup of a referral network going from audiologists to other medical professionals, as well as guidelines for when such cognition-based referrals are necessary. Finally, audiologists must decide what cognitive profiles would justify different hearing aid algorithms and other technologies. These questions will not be easy to answer, and the road ahead will be long. Despite this, with SIN and other hearing impairments continuing to be underdiagnosed, cognitive testing should be a top priority for researchers and audiologists alike.

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